

Cryptocurrency Transactions and Exchange Rate Movements in Nigeria: A Vector Autoregression Approach

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Abstract

This paper delved into ascertaining the influence of the cryptocurrency market on the exchange rate situation in Nigeria. The study utilized monthly data from January 2018 to May 2025. The analytical techniques hinge around the ordinary least squares (OLS) approach and the vector error correction model. The OLS indicated that both the Bitcoin and Ethereum transactions in the cryptocurrency market positively affected the exchange rate in Nigeria. Thus, rising crypto market transactions therefore spurs exchange rate depreciation. The impulse response function obtained from the VAR model further indicated that exchange rate responded to shocks in crypto market transactions during the study period hence, the Nigerian foreign exchange market is not immune to crypto market distortions. The paper therefore recommended that the Nigerian monetary authority should resort to the regulation of the crypto market in order to curb excessive and uncontrolled transactions which can trigger unnecessary fluctuations of the domestic currency.

Keywords: Bitcoin, Ethereum, Blockchain, Financial Institutions, Monetary Policy

Introduction

The level of cryptocurrency transactions is believed to have some impact on the domestic economic condition as it affects the substitutability of the domestic currency with digital assets thereby constraining the effectiveness of monetary policy in the economy. Cryptocurrency may have a variety of effects on monetary policy, including improved financial inclusion, less control over the money supply, and more competition (Karau, 2021; Benigno, 2022). Since cryptocurrencies are decentralized, they are less vulnerable to the monetary policy instruments that conventional institutions employ, such the amount of money in circulation or fluctuations in interest rates, than fiat currencies. Cryptocurrencies may also put pressure on central banks to preserve the stability and strength of their currencies as a result of growing competition. The decentralized software framework and steady supply that underpin cryptocurrencies like Bitcoin also controls the exchange rate and guards against inflation.

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In Africa, (TripleA, 2024) reported that about 44 million crypto users in Africa in 2024. Conventional financial institutions and regulatory frameworks have been put to the test by cryptocurrencies, which are digital or virtual currencies that run on decentralized blockchain technology and employ encryption for security (Baur, Hong, & Lee, 2018). The most well-known of these virtual currencies are Bitcoin, Ethereum, and other altcoins, which are becoming more and more popular all over the world, especially in developing nations like Nigeria (Benedikter & Cohen, 2021).

The use of cryptocurrencies has increased significantly in Nigeria, which is now among the top nations in terms of both peer-to-peer trade volumes and cryptocurrency adoption (Chainalysis, 2020). The high rate of inflation of the Nigerian naira (NGN), restricted access to foreign currencies, unstable economic conditions, and a young, tech-savvy populace looking for alternative investment options are some of the elements driving this trend (Ogege & Acha, 2021). Citing dangers including money laundering, volatility, and capital flight, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) has voiced worries about the uncontrolled character of cryptocurrencies, arguing that they might further devalue the naira (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2021).

Many Nigerians have turned to cryptocurrencies as a store of value and a way to send money abroad as a result of the naira's ongoing decline versus major world currencies. This change has raised questions about how much cryptocurrency affects the naira's value. While some say that using cryptocurrencies might lessen the impact of exchange rate volatility and inflation, others argue that it worsens capital outflows and undermines trust in the local currency (Kshetri & Voas, 2018). Examining the possible connection between cryptocurrency use and naira value is crucial given the growing significance of digital currencies in Nigeria's financial system. Policymakers, investors, and other stakeholders who want to balance financial innovation and economic stability must comprehend this link.

The appeal of cryptocurrencies in Nigeria has endured in spite of regulatory opposition. The Central Bank of Nigeria banned banks and other financial institutions from assisting cryptocurrency transactions in February 2021 (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2021). This action, which was intended to reduce financial risks and preserve monetary policy control, unintentionally forced a large portion of cryptocurrency activity onto peer-to-peer (P2P) and decentralized networks, making regulatory monitoring even more difficult Olayemi (2022).

Paradoxically, it's possible that these limitations have made cryptocurrency-related transactions opaquer, which has led to worries about capital flight and decreased liquidity in the traditional banking industry.

The volume of cryptocurrency transactions over the years has exhibited some sort of gyrations given the level of fear and greed within the crypto ecosystem. A unique statistic created by CoinMarketCap (CMC), the Fear and Greed Index gauges the general mood in the cryptocurrency market. excessive fear is represented by a lower number on this index, which goes from 0 to 100, whereas excessive greed is represented by a greater value. It aids investors in comprehending the market's emotional condition, which might affect their decisions to purchase or sell. The indicator gives information on whether the market is overpriced (excessive greed) or underpriced (extreme fear). There are several applications for the CMC Fear and Greed Index:

- a) **Market Sentiment Analysis:** You can determine the general state of the cryptocurrency market by looking at the index's current value. A high value, for instance, can be a sign that investors are too greedy, which might mean that the market is overheated and ready for a correction. On the other hand, a low value might indicate that prices are falling due to fear, which could lead to possibilities for purchases.
- b) **Contrarian Strategy:** A contrarian investing strategy is one in which some investors employ the index. The concept is to "be fearful when others are greedy and greedy when others are fearful." Extreme anxiety might suggest a purchasing opportunity, while extreme greed could be a clue to think about selling assets.
- c) **Complementary Analysis:** Make better judgments by utilizing the index in conjunction with other analytical instruments and indicators. The index is a tool for measuring sentiment; thus, it should not be used in isolation, it is crucial to keep in mind.

The pattern of the CMC Fear and Greed Index and how it reflects activities in the crypto market is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The cycle of market emotions

Source: <https://www.bitdegree.org/>

The dynamics of the crypto market transactions (with reference to Bitcoin and Ethereum) are given in Figure 2 and Figure 3.

Figure 2: Bitcoin volume of transaction, 2018Q1 to 2025Q2

Figure 3: Ethereum volume of transaction, 2018Q1 to 2025Q2

Given the dynamics of the core cryptocurrencies over the years, the exchange rate situation in Nigeria has been depreciating drastically as shown in Figure 4. Within the period under review, both Bitcoin and Ethereum transaction reached their highest level in the first quarter of 2021 with another peak recorded in the fourth quarter of 2024.

The Nigerian naira has showcased consistent depreciation over the years as it moved from ₦305.81/\$1 in the first quarter of 2018 to ₦381.00 in the fourth quarter of 2020. This depreciation continued up to ₦412.44/\$1 and ₦445.71/\$1 in the fourth quarter of 2021 and 2022 respectively.

Figure 4: Exchange rate movements in Nigeria, 2018Q1 to 2025Q2

The depreciating trend continues in the 2023 to 2024 periods as it reached ₦843.80/\$1 and ₦1,621.53/\$1 in the fourth quarter of 2023 and 2024 respectively. The naira however appreciated slightly in the first quarter of 2025 against the fourth quarter of 2024 as it appreciated to ₦1,522.71/\$1 before depreciating again to ₦1,590.40/\$1 in the second quarter of 2025.

Literature Review

Studies have been conducted to establish the nexus between cryptocurrency transactions and exchange rate dynamics. Olayemi and Adedayo (2021), for example, performed a time-series study of cryptocurrency trading volumes and exchange rate variations in Nigeria and discovered a substantial negative link between the value of the Naira in the parallel market and a rise in Bitcoin transactions. According to their results, the demand for the Naira declines as more people use cryptocurrencies for transactions and savings, particularly in uncertain economic times, which further depreciates the currency.

Uchenna and Emmanuel (2020) used panel data from eight countries, including Nigeria, to investigate how the introduction of cryptocurrencies affected the efficacy of monetary policy in Sub-Saharan Africa. According to their research, cryptocurrencies can partially replace native currencies in nations with high rates of inflation and exchange rate volatility. They came to the conclusion that the central bank's capacity to regulate inflation and stabilize the local currency is hampered by the expanding usage of decentralized digital currencies, which erodes the monetary policy transmission mechanism.

The autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) modeling was used in additional empirical research by Bamidele and Okonkwo (2022) to investigate the short- and long-term impacts of bitcoin use on Nigeria's exchange rate. Their findings demonstrated that, over time, cryptocurrency transactions—particularly those using stablecoins—are linked to a decline in the value of the Naira because they promote capital flight and lessen the need to keep local currency. Their research also showed that the use of cryptocurrencies increased during times of macroeconomic shocks or political unrest, which increased pressure on the foreign exchange market. These results are in line with those of Adegbite and Yusuf (2019), who examined how digital financial innovations affect West African currency replacement. They discovered that people are more likely to use alternative payment methods, like cryptocurrencies, if their

confidence in national currencies declines as a result of inflation and erratic monetary policy. This helps to gradually displace fiat money in some economic sectors.

Jimoh and Benjamin (2020) used data from August 2015 to December 2019 using the Granger causality test, EGARCH 1, and GARCH 1 algorithms to examine the relationship between Nigeria's stock market price, exchange rate, and the two most traded cryptocurrencies, Ethereum and Bitcoin. The results show that stock market prices are more affected by the price volatility of Bitcoin and Ethereum than by the exchange rate in Nigeria. The analysis also shows a one-way causal link between Ethereum and Bitcoin and the all-share index.

Several studies have examined the ways in which government laws, technical adoption, and demographic variables impact the relationship between digital assets and local currency performance in Nigeria, in addition to the empirical literature already in existence on cryptocurrencies and currency value. For instance, Eze and Nwachukwu (2021) examined how the adoption of cryptocurrencies is influenced by the youth population and rising smartphone penetration in major areas like Lagos, Abuja, and Port Harcourt. According to their research, tech-savvy young Nigerians frequently turn to cryptocurrencies as a way to preserve their wealth and promote financial inclusion since they face significant unemployment and restricted access to traditional financial services. The demand dynamics for the Naira are changed by this growing acceptance by a sizable section of the populace, which also opens up new avenues for investment and savings that go beyond established monetary regulations.

Ibikunle and Akutson (2022) investigated the impact of cryptocurrency volatility on Nigeria's foreign exchange market using data from September 2019 to September 2021. The VAR-Multivariate GARCH analytical framework is used to determine how foreign currency returns affect the price returns of four of Nigeria's largest cryptocurrencies. The average spillovers of cryptocurrencies are positively impacted by foreign exchange, according to the findings, which also showed that past errors in the foreign exchange market are vulnerable to external volatility. In addition to recommending low-leverage contracts and suitable diversification strategies to prevent the high risks associated with cryptocurrencies, which are prone to volatility, the study found that cryptocurrencies are helpful tools for hedging against financial uncertainty.

Empirical research has also emphasized how inflation predictions affect the correlation between cryptocurrency and currency value. In order to protect themselves from dwindling

buying power, consumers are increasingly turning their Naira assets into cryptocurrency as inflation forecasts grow, according to Adebisi and Olayiwola (2021). According to their survey-based study, even Nigerian low-income individuals are beginning to see cryptocurrencies as a hedge against unstable economic conditions. The authors contend that such actions increase currency market volatility by pushing the Naira down, particularly during times of political upheaval, economic instability, or poor policy management.

Recent study by (Udoh, Akpan, & Bagudo, 2024) explored how cryptocurrencies influence exchange rate volatility in Nigeria using VAR model from the first quarter of 2015 to the fourth quarter of 2022. The impulse response function analyses portrayed that Bitcoin prices meaningfully impacted the exchange rate. (Safiyanu, Haruna, Gurin, & Bayero, 2022) used the ARDL analysis on monthly time series data covering January 2015 to December 2020 to examine the impact of Bitcoin on Nigeria's currency rate. Results show that the price of Bitcoin has a significant influence on both the short- and long-term exchange rate. Mallick and Mallik (2023) used multiple regression analysis to investigate the connection between cryptocurrencies and Indian currency foreign exchange rates using daily data from December 2019 to June 2021. The study's conclusions show that, except from YEN and Ethereum, as well as USD, Binance Coin, and Litecoin, there is no discernible relationship between the exchange rates of cryptocurrencies and Indian currency.

The existing body of knowledge have established that there is a possible link between cryptocurrency transactions and exchange rate in an economy. This study is therefore geared towards establishing the nexus between cryptocurrency transactions and exchange rate in Nigeria by using recent data from January 2018 to May 2025. This study differs from existing study by considering how the crypto market fear and greed index also affects the crypto market transactions and the exchange rate in Nigeria. Our study utilizes the Vector Autoregressive (VAR) technique to measure how exchange rate responds to shocks in cryptocurrency transactions. The OLS technique of estimation is also incorporated in the analysis to establish the magnitude of the effect of cryptocurrency transactions on exchange rate condition in Nigeria.

Methodology

This study is an attempt to explore how exchange rate responds to crypto market transactions in Nigeria. Consequently, the model for the study is expressed as follows:

$$EXCH_t = f(CRPTO_t) \quad (1)$$

In which EXCH is the exchange rate and CRPTO signifies crypto market transactions. By incorporating key crypto market transactions into Equation (1), we can then have

$$EXCH_t = (BTCV_t, ETHV_t, CMFG_t) \quad (2)$$

where BTCV is the volume of Bitcoin transaction, ETHV is the volume of Ethereum transaction, and CMFG is the crypto market fear and greed index. The choice of Bitcoin and Ethereum in the analysis is based on the fact that they have the highest market capitalization.

Equation (2) can be expressed in its econometric form as follows:

$$EXCH_t = \theta_0 + \theta_1 BTCV_t + \theta_2 CMFG_t + \mu_t \quad (3a)$$

and

$$EXCH_t = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1 ETHV_t + \gamma_2 CMFG_t + \mu_t \quad (3b)$$

for which θ_0 and γ_0 are the constant terms, and θ_1 to θ_2 and γ_1 and γ_2 are the partial slope coefficient of the regressors. It is expected that $\theta_1 > 0$, $\theta_2 > 0$, $\gamma_1 > 0$ and $\gamma_2 > 0$ to portray that changes in the crypto market could have a direct effect on exchange rate (exchange rate depreciation).

Data for the study were obtained from secondary sources. For instance, data on exchange rate was obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin, data on both volume of Bitcoin and Ethereum transactions were obtained from Coinmarketcap while data on crypto market fear and greed index was obtained from BitDegree, a crypto platform. The data so utilized for the study is monthly data from January 2018 to May 2025, constituting a total of eighty-nine (89) observations.

The analytical technique used in the study were the ordinary least squares (OLS) method of estimation and the vector autoregressive (VAR) model. The OLS approach facilitates the

estimation of the partial slope coefficients to see magnitude of the effect of crypto market transactions on the exchange rate.

The VAR model helps in generating the impulse response functions to show how exchange rate responds to shocks in the crypto market. The VAR(p) model for the study is therefore specified as follows:

$$EXCH_t = \pi_{10} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \pi_{11} EXCH_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \pi_{12} BTCV_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \pi_{13} ETHV_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \pi_{14} CMFG_{t-i} + \varepsilon_{1t} \quad (4)$$

$$BTCV_t = \pi_{20} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \pi_{21} EXCH_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \pi_{22} BTCV_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \pi_{23} ETHV_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \pi_{24} CMFG_{t-i} + \varepsilon_{2t} \quad (5)$$

$$ETHV_t = \pi_{30} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \pi_{31} EXCH_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \pi_{32} BTCV_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \pi_{33} ETHV_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \pi_{34} CMFG_{t-i} + \varepsilon_{3t} \quad (6)$$

$$CMFG_t = \pi_{40} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \pi_{41} EXCH_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \pi_{42} BTCV_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \pi_{43} ETHV_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \pi_{44} CMFG_{t-i} + \varepsilon_{4t} \quad (7)$$

Equation (4) through Equation (7) are the VAR(2) specification where the optima lag (based on the Akaike Information Criterion, AIC) is obtained to be 2. Estimation of the above equation generates the VAR estimates of which further analysis can be conducted to obtain the impulse response function and the variance decomposition.

Empirical Findings

The Ordinary Least Squares Estimation

The empirical analysis starts from the estimation of the OLS model of which Table 1 presents the result for the study.

Table 1: The ordinary least squares estimate

Dependent Variable: EXCH				
Method: OLS				
Variables	Model I		Model II	
	Coefficient	Probability	Coefficient	Probability
BTCV	91.41540 [4.384686]	0.0000	-----	-----
ETHV	-----	-----	85.06391 [4.320708]	0.0000
CMFG	3.627039 [1.551849]	0.1244	3.726554 [1.593282]	0.1148
C	-1937.696 [-3.751514]	0.0003	-1711.176 [-3.619530]	0.0005
R-squared	0.264169		0.260216	
Adjusted R-squared	0.246855		0.242809	
F-statistic	15.25783		14.94918	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000002		0.000003	

Some: Estimated by the authors using Eviews

The empirical result presented in Table 1 captures the OLS estimates to ascertain how the selected crypto market variables impact on the exchange rate situation in Nigeria. In the first model, the impact of bitcoin transaction on exchange rate was captured. The result portrayed that a rise in the volume of Bitcoin transaction initiated a positive and significant effect on exchange rate. Therefore, a rising volume of Bitcoin transaction propels exchange rate depreciation significantly. From the coefficient, a \$1 increase in the volume of Bitcoin

transaction will lead to a \$91.42 increase in the exchange rate. Therefore, exchange rate is more responsive to changes in the volume of Bitcoin transactions. The crypto market fear and greed index do not exert any significant influence on exchange rate movements in Nigeria.

In the second model, the influence of the volume of Ethereum transactions on exchange rate was captured. The result shows that the volume of Ethereum transactions initiated a positive and significant effect on exchange rate in Nigeria. The estimated model indicated that a \$1 increase in the volume of Ethereum transaction initiates \$85.06 increase in exchange rate. Thus, increased volume of Ethereum transactions initiates a significant increase in exchange rate depreciation in Nigeria.

Vector Autoregression

The impulse response functions are generated from estimation of the VAR model to show how shocks in the crypto market could trigger some responses in the exchange rate market. Such responses are reflected in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Response of exchange rate to shocks in the crypto market

The impulse response function indicates that exchange rate responded negatively to shocks in the volume of Bitcoin transaction up to the 8th months after which the variable responds positively to such shocks. On the contrary, exchange rate responded negatively to shocks in the volume of Ethereum transactions throughout the period. Meanwhile, exchange rate responded negatively to shocks in crypto market fear and greed index up to the 3rd period after which such response turned positive all through.

It could also be observed that both the volume of Bitcoin and Ethereum transactions responded positively to shocks in exchange rate throughout the periods. Further, both the volume of Bitcoin and Ethereum transactions responded positively to shocks in crypto market fear and greed index throughout the periods. The volume of Bitcoin transactions responded

positively to shocks in the volume of Ethereum transactions and the volume of Ethereum transaction also responded positively to shocks in the volume of Bitcoin transaction.

Stability Test

To ascertain the stability to the VAR estimates, the inverse root of autoregressive (AR) characteristic polynomial is utilized and the result is given in Figure 6.

Figure 6: The inverse root of AR characteristic polynomial

The inverse root characteristic presented in Figure 6 portrays that all the points lie within the unit circle. Consequently, the VAR model estimates are stable for policy making.

Discussion of Findings

The interaction between cryptocurrency transactions and exchange rate movements in Nigeria has portrayed concerned result. The findings have indicated that both Bitcoin and Ethereum transactions have exerted positive and significant effect on exchange rate in Nigeria. The implication of this is that a rise in cryptocurrency transactions is an indication of a rising

demand for the dollar relative to the naira. This therefore put pressure on the foreign exchange rate thereby prompting a depreciation of the naira. As such, greater crypto transactions will exacerbate the naira-dollar exchange rate situation. The impulse response function further showcase that exchange rate responded to shocks in cryptocurrency transactions, thus portraying the fact that the Nigerian foreign exchange market is not immune to shocks arising from the cryptocurrency market.

Conclusion

The cryptocurrency market is a volatile ecosystem involving a lot of speculations, market sentiments and ‘gut behaviour’. Despite this volatile pattern of the market, it offers huge gains to investors, while a greater segment of the market makes huge losses. This risk and sentiments embedded in the market therefore generates series of fear and greed within the crypto ecosystem. Nigerians are highly involved in cryptocurrency investments and trading which they see such as an alternative source of storing wealth and taking advantage of the swings in the market at a risk. This behaviour therefore makes scholars to believe that crypto transactions worsen capital outflows and undermines trust in the local currency. Our study examined the nexus between cryptocurrency transactions and exchange rate movements in Nigeria and we have noticed that both bitcoin and Ethereum transactions undermines the value of the domestic currency. However, this must not be taken to mean that investment in cryptocurrency is deleterious to the Nigerian economy. The established findings is a justification for the need to regulate the crypto market in Nigeria, rather than rendering it illegal. An attempt to curb trading or investment in crypto currency will further worsen the situation thereby creating avenue for informal transactions through peer-to-peer which even far riskier. Our conclusion therefore is that Nigeria should follow international standards on cryptocurrency market since countries like the USA, China, United Kingdom, El Salvador and Finland have crypto reserves.

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